

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF PROBLEMS OF LINGUISTIC STUDY

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Abstract: This article deals with the origin of the science of linguistics, its social nature, about language, its function, internal structure, classification, the laws of specific languages, historical development.

Key words: Linguistics, grammar, linguistics, internal structure, structural linguistics, comparative-historical linguistics, special linguistics, general linguistics, lexicography, ethnolinguistics, psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics, phonetics, phonology, word formation, word combination, morphology.

Introduction:

Linguistics or Linguistics is a science that studies languages. There are practical and theoretical types of linguistics, and theoretical linguistics studies the structure of language and its meaning. It covers the disciplines of grammar (*the structure and transformation of words*), syntax (*the rules for joining words into phrases and sentences*), and phonology (*the study of language using abstract sounds*). Applied linguistics mainly deals with the practical application of theoretical knowledge learned in linguistics. Applied linguistics includes learning and teaching foreign languages.

Linguistics is a science about language, its social nature, function, internal structure, classification, laws of operation (*activity*) of specific languages, historical development. According to its purpose and task, there are several directions (*fields*) of linguistics: general linguistics is a field that studies language as a phenomenon characteristic of a person in general, the main task of which is to identify and illuminate the most general characteristics of the languages of the world; private linguistics is a field that studies some characteristics of a language; applied linguistics is a direction that develops methods for solving practical problems related to language use (*experimental phonetics, lexicography, linguostatistics, transcription, transliteration, etc.*); mathematical linguistics, structural linguistics, comparative-historical linguistics and other fields such as paralinguistics, ethnolinguistics, psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics study language features related to the activity of the speaker (person) in society.

In addition to these areas, linguistics has many branches and departments that study specific levels and units in each language: semasiology studies the meanings of language units; phonetics and phonology examine the sound construction of language; lexicology and phraseology study the lexical material of the language. The object of study of word formation is the methods of word formation and the productivity of these methods, while grammar (morphology and syntax) studies word changes and the laws of combining words into sentences and phrases. Each branch of linguistics can have smaller (smaller) special branches. For example, within lexicology there is a department of onomastics, which in turn is divided

into anthroponymics, toponymics, etc. Dialectology studies regional differentiation (*differentiation*) of a particular language. Each of these sections examines the current state of the language and its historical development (see Diachrony, Synchrony). Branches of linguistics that study world languages, their families and groups: Arabistics (*Arabic studies*), Germanic studies, Turkic studies, Slavic studies, Finno-Ugric studies and other languages interaction, theory and practice of creating auxiliary international languages, as well as interlinguistics and translation theory learns.

Linguistics as a science is important in learning native and foreign languages, developing and improving terminology, scientific interpretation of linguistic texts, machine translation; made it possible to solve the problems of the interrelationship of real and imaginary things (*materiality and ideality*), to draw theoretical conclusions for the correct understanding of social consciousness and the human being as a social being. The problem of the relationship between language and thought, linguistic and logical units (magnitudes) is studied simultaneously by linguistics and philosophy. Descriptive (comparative, confrontational, contrastive, typological), historical (comparative-historical, comparative) and normative-stylistic (normative) methods can be indicated as the main linguistic methods. Linguistics also has special research methods - observation of linguistic phenomena, linguistic experiment, linguistic modeling, linguistic interpretation methods. Linguistics emerged at the border between philosophy and philology.

The study of linguistic problems first started in Ancient India. Ancient Indian Linguistics mil. avv. It arises as a result of interpreting the Vedas, created before the 6th century, from the point of view of language, and mil. avv. It rose to prominence thanks to Panini's grammar, which lived in the 5th-4th centuries. This work consists of 3,996 rules written in verse, describing Sanskrit phonetics and grammar. In Greece, language was studied in relation to logic, as well as from the point of view of its grammatical construction (views of Heraclitus and Democritus, works of Plato and Aristotle, "Grammar" of Dionysius of Thrace, etc.). Classification of words into categories began with Aristotle. The maturity of ancient Greek linguistics is connected with the activity of Greek linguists in Alexandria and partly in Pergan (Asia Minor). Greek grammar was written by representatives of the Alexandrian grammar school (3rd-2nd centuries BC). On the basis of Greek linguistics, Latin linguistics was born.

Later Arabic (*grammar schools in Baghdad, Kufa. Basra*), Jewish, Aramaic (the works of Andalusian philologists of the 9th-12th centuries) and Turkish (the works of Koshgari and Zamakhshari) are the source of scientific description. The development of linguistics in the Middle Ages is associated with the names of Arabic as well as non-Arab philologists who worked in Arabic. Central Asian scholars such as Abu Rayhan Beruni, Ibn Sina, Mahmud Koshgari, Zamakhshari, and Javahari have made a great contribution to the development of Arabic Linguistics.

Zamakhsharians made great innovations in world linguistics in the field of lexicology and lexicography. Mahmud Koshgari and Zamakhshariy gained fame as the first linguists who used the comparative historical method and typology in linguistics by comparing and contrasting Turkish dialects and languages belonging to different families with their works "Devonu Lugati-Turk", "Mukaddimat uladab". Philological sciences also developed in the Far East, especially in China and Japan. Linguistics in Russia developed from the 15th to the 16th centuries.

In the work "*Russian Grammar*" by M. V. Lomonosov, the phonetic, morphological, and partially syntactic features of the Russian literary language were consistently described for the first time. During the Renaissance, interest in the cultural heritage of the ancient world stimulated the development of classical philology. Along with this, the study of new, modern European languages on a logical basis began. The application of the comparative methodology and the principle of historicity laid the foundation for comparative historical linguistics, which has achieved success in the study of the kinship of languages, the genealogy of languages: the development of classification, the study of the historical development of related languages, language families, mainly the Indo-European language family, the restoration of the ancient state of languages, etc. German scientists *F. Bopp*, *Ya. Grimm*, *A. F. Pott*, *A. Schleicher*, *A. Dietz*, Danish *R. K. Rusk*, Czech *Y. Dobrovsky*, Austrian *F. Miklosich*, Russian scientist *A. H. Vostokov* and others made great contributions. The foundations of general Linguistics, the understanding of language as "activity" and "product of activity", the doctrine of the external and internal form of language, the typological classification of languages and other problems were developed by the German scientist *W. Humboldt*. His ideas greatly influenced the development of several areas of Western linguistics in the 19th and 20th centuries. *T. Humboldt* reasonably stated that it should get rid of logic and have its own method, that language has a systemic nature, and that it is a social phenomenon in which it has 2 aspects - sound and meaning. In the middle of the 19th century, *A. Schleicher* tried to apply biological theories in linguistics.

A school of young grammarians (*German scientists A. Leskin, K. Brugmann, G. Osthof, B. Delbrück, G. Paul, etc.*) was formed on the basis of criticism of linguistic naturalism, which focused on the study of living languages. Representatives of this school brought the development of comparative historical linguistics to a new stage. In the 19th century, the main branches of Indo-European linguistics (*Hellenistics, Greek studies, Romance studies, German studies, Slavic studies, Celtic studies, etc.*) were fully formed. The principles of the comparative historical method developed for Indo-European languages were also applied to other languages that do not belong to this family. In this way, fields such as Semitology, Turkic studies, Finno-Ugric studies, and African studies are formed. In the development of linguistics at the beginning of the 20th century, the works of *Ferdinand de Saussure*, first of all, "*Course of General Linguistics*" (1916) played an important role. *Saussure* created a sign theory of language, studied synchrony and diachrony, internal linguistics, external linguistics and other problems. The ideas of *Ferdinand de Saussure* are further developed in the later schools of linguistic structuralism: Prague linguistic school - functional linguistics, Copenhagen linguistic circle (*glossematics*), Geneva school, American descriptive linguistics.

Along with the structural currents, other directions and views began to develop: the psychological direction (*the works of the German scientists H. Steinthal and W. Wundt; the Russian scientist V.V. Potebilanya also joins this direction*), neurolinguistics and other materialistic worldviews, with the wide spread of experimental phonetics and linguistic geography. began to develop. Later, in linguistics, new directions and departments: psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics, ethnolinguistics, semiotic linguistics, transformational linguistics, text linguistics and others appear. In modern foreign linguistics, along with materialist theories, there are also theories based on idealistic principles (*for example, the theory of linguistic relativity or new Humboldtism*).

The history of Uzbek linguistics began with the researches of Mahmud Koshghari and Zamakhshari and followed a long, historical path of development. From the 15th century to the 20s of the 20th century, special attention was paid to the practical aspects of learning the Uzbek language (*Lexicography, Dictionary*), many bilingual (*Uzbek-Persian, Uzbek-Turkish, Uzbek-Russian and vice versa*) dictionaries were created - the lexicology and lexicography departments of linguistics developed. The study of the Uzbek language in the current sense began in the 20s of the 20th century. As a result of the language policy carried out during the Soviet period, overestimation of the position of the Russian language in society, certain shortcomings and defects were allowed in the study, description and research of the language and linguistic phenomena (*especially in the study of the grammar of the Uzbek language*), but Uzbek linguistics developed and achieved certain achievements. *Fitrat, K. Ramazan, Otajon Hashim, S. Ibrohimov, Olim Usman, Z. Ma'rufov, Fakhri Kamal, A. Gulomov, F. Abdullayev, Sh. Shoabduragmanov, G. Abdurahmonov, A. Rustamov, M. Askarova, Kh. Doniyorov, Sh. Shukurov, Sh. Our scientists such as Rahmatullayev, M. Mirtojiyev, E. Begmatov* and others contributed greatly. Problems of linguistics in Uzbekistan are studied by the Institute of Type and Literature named after Alisher Navoi of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, as well as by departments of higher educational institutions related to language teaching, and a special journal "*Uzbek Language and Literature*" is published.

In conclusion, language unity and its free development is one of the main characteristics of a nation. The difference between the national language and the folk language is that it has a literary form. This form of the national language is common to every member of this nation and every dialect. The cultural heritage of every nation is reflected in this language. Linguistics is a science that studies different languages, their origin, history, methods of use, and languages in general.

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